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Introducing Sustainability in Engineering Education Curricula: an achievable outcome or a utopia?

A. C. Alves¹

Assistant Professor

ALGORITMI Research Center, School of Engineering, University of Minho

Guimarães, Portugal

E-mail: anabela@dps.uminho.pt

C. R. Colombo

Professor Adjunto

Departamento de Engenharia de Produção, Universidade Federal Rio G. do Norte

Natal, Rio Grande do Norte, Brazil

E-mail: cilianacolombo@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Sustainability, social and environmental responsibility become more and more relevant for professional engineering. This is recognized by universities that are doing their best to introduce these issues in the curricula. But this is not a trivial issue and their integration with the existent and news issues must be total. So, a lot of authors, academics, researchers are always concerned with this and are trying different approaches and learning methodologies in order to achieve successfully sustainability integration. This paper presents and explores some of these approaches and perspectives from four different countries: Portugal, Brazil, Canada and Spain. The study is based on the analyses of papers, presentations and debate session results from a previous engineering education conference. In spite of the reduced sample, it was a lived sample that shared personal and team perspectives about the issue through the debate. Also, it is discussed how the participants introduced sustainability, corroborating that this integration could be an achievable outcome and not a utopia.

Conference Key Areas: Sustainability, Engineering Education, Research

Keywords: Sustainability, Engineering Education

INTRODUCTION

Pappas [1] defined a sustainable society as *“A sustainable society possesses the ability to survive and prosper, not just with respect to environmental resources, but also with respect to quality of life as it pertains to social, economic, technical and individual contexts, and especially the values and conditions that promote continued human prosperity and growth (...). A sustainable society meets these needs simultaneously,*

¹ Corresponding Author

A. C. Alves

anabela@dps.uminho.pt

and in the context of human respect and the ability to negotiate differences without violence.”.

The same author [1][2], assuming that individual sustainability dimension is probably the most influential factor in the success of activities in other dimensions of sustainability, proposed that the individual's understanding of the complexities and interconnections between their own sustainability contexts is necessary to further understanding of the community and global sustainability. Thus, the promotion of true learning about sustainability is, firstly, to develop in these individuals the understanding and appropriation of the values of individual sustainability and the ability to change oneself intentionally.

In this sense, universities have a significant role in promoting the Sustainability concept in its different spheres: teaching, research, extension, and management. In fact, Education for Sustainable Development (EDS) has been on the agenda of many universities especially promoted and guided by the Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (DESD) (2005-2014) [3], which was completed with some achievements and its follow-up, the Global Action Program (GAP) on EDS [4].

Universities have begun the way to ESD, but there are still new concepts in most universities [5–7] or they are far from a complete integration into university operations and curricula [8–10]. Only 15 of more than 14,000 universities worldwide have published their sustainability reports [11]. However, as it has been shown, it is accepted that education is a key element in the change and transformation of behavior and practices towards a sustainable society [12].

Attending to this context, the main objective pursued by this study was to analyze different approaches towards Engineering Education for Sustainable Development (EESD) from different countries and contexts presented in a real and live debate session of a previous Engineering Education conference. Also, in this paper are presented the results of the discussion among the authors of the proposed approaches and others participants in the debate session. As a secondary objective was expected to answer or contribute to the answer or make deeper questions about future challenges in a real implementation of EESD based on real case studies.

This paper is divided into five main sections. After this introduction, a brief literature review is presented. The research methodology is presented in the second section. The study context is presented in section three. A debate to discuss the sustainability theme in engineering curricula took place in this study context which main results are highlighted in the fourth section. Finally, conclusions are drawn up in section five.

1. BRIEF LITERATURE REVIEW

Attending to the sociocultural complexity in which we live and the multiplicity of fields in which sustainability can and should be worked on, its concept and dimensions are not yet a consensus in the literature, assuming a polysemy and multi-disciplinary sense applicable to different situations, contexts, and objectives. Approaches varies according to different areas of knowledge and often within the same area. Likewise, Sustainability and Sustainable Development (SD) are approached as common concepts, albeit with differences between them.

Since the sixties, Sustainability has been aimed into the direction of development when, in the Brundtland Report [13], the concept of SD was proposed. This concept evolved, not only to harmonize but to integrate development with the environment when the concepts of Sustainability and SD emerged to translate this integration. Thus,

from the 1980s, the term SD was assumed, whose concept was widely diffused assuming this as a form of development that seeks to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to attend to theirs as well.

It should also be noted that although the perception of the need to remain within limits of recovery has begun in the nature dimension, it is necessary to broaden the spectrum of what needs to be maintained, which must not be destroyed, as by cultural diversity. The idea of sustainability, then, it is not restricted to the beings of nature, it also involves other dimensions [14]. From the first five Pappas [1] dimensions: Social-cultural, Economic-financial, Environmental or Ecological, Technical or Technological, and Individual; three more were added by different authors: Relational or Convivial, Territorial or Geographical and Epistemological [15].

To introduce this model of development in the society, UNESCO [4] proposed that sustainability should be integrated at different levels of education, calling it ESD. According to UNESCO [4], ESD empowers learners to take informed decisions and responsible actions for environmental integrity, economic viability, and a just society, for present and future generations, while respecting cultural diversity. It is about lifelong learning and is an integral part of quality education. ESD is holistic and transformational education which addresses learning content and outcomes, pedagogy and the learning environment. It achieves its purpose by transforming society.

The ESD must be integrated into the learning content by integrating critical issues, such as climate change, biodiversity, disaster risk reduction (DRR), and sustainable consumption and production (SCP), into the curriculum. Also, ESD should be integrated in the pedagogy and learning environments by designing teaching and learning in an interactive, learner-centred way that enables exploratory, action-oriented and transformative learning and by rethinking learning environments – physical as well as virtual and online – to inspire learners to act for sustainability.

Additionally, should be integrated in societal transformation by empowering learners of any age, in any education setting, to transform themselves and the society they live in order to: 1) Enabling a transition to greener economies and societies (equipping learners with skills for 'green jobs' and motivating people to adopt sustainable lifestyles); 2) Empowering people to be 'global citizens' who engage and assume active roles, both locally and globally, to face and to resolve global challenges and ultimately to become proactive contributors to creating a more just, peaceful, tolerant, inclusive, secure and sustainable world.

The integration of sustainability into higher education, according to Wals [16], could follow two approaches: "bolt-on": adding new courses and modules that have elements of ESD; 2) "built-in": integrating sustainability in existing studies and research programs as well as in staff development. Resembling these, Rusinko [17] previously proposed four forms of integration that vary, depending on the combination of two variables: the maintenance of the general structures of the degree (or creating a new structure) for the implementation of sustainable aspects and the focus given to sustainability (specific for each discipline or more cross-cutting and interdisciplinary).

In addition, and related with the responsibility to implement ESD, this could be a process: 1) top-down process, posing it at the institutional level and transmitting it to schools, departments, degrees, and faculty; and/or 2) bottom-up, from active faculty but with definitive need of institutional support [8]. Other studies about how to introduce sustainability in curricula could be seen, namely, in Hansen et al. [18], Allen et al. [19], Dewulf et al. [20], Holgaard et al. [21] and Colombo et al. [22].

Working sustainability as specific disciplines is of fundamental importance, by one hand, because as Dewulf et al. [20] said when it is only transversal can have negative

points such as, the fact of being worked by a non-specialist teacher in the area the subject becomes fragmented in other disciplines and, thus, there are overlap or aspects not covered, and to integrate it into another discipline does not have a logical sequence.

On the other hand, the lack of a transversal approach in all disciplines can put the theme as disconnected from the rest and thus the perception of its importance is diminished. Therefore, the teaching-learning methodology adopted is fundamental to minimize these negative points. For instance, project-based teaching, still with different denominations as Fourez [23] did when he proposed his “Island of Rationality” method to the diffused Project Based Learning [24,25], has already been highlighted as the most appropriate method for the construction of rooted sustainability knowledge for the training of future professionals.

This methodology is adequate for the interdisciplinary structure of education, in which there is the interaction of all agents of education. At the same time, the work is more interdisciplinary, promoting the interaction and integration of knowledge both for students and educators, thus favoring that Sustainability is placed at the same level as the other themes addressed in the different disciplines. Some examples have been exposed that evidence this [18,26–30]. The promotion of true learning about sustainability firstly involves developing in individuals the understanding and appropriation of the values of individual sustainability and the ability to change oneself intentionally. Thus, teaching-learning approaches should enable this objective of individual transformation to be achieved so that collective transformation is possible in the search for a sustainable society.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this paper, the authors intend to discuss the introduction of Sustainability in EE curricula, based on their active participation in a debate session of an EE conference organized in 2016. In the context of the conference, four authors of submitted and approved papers were invited by conference organizers to participate in this specific session. These papers had in common case studies and studies of sustainability integration in engineering degrees and programs from different countries: Spain, Portugal, Canada, and Brazil.

From the debate discussion, moderated by one of this paper authors, and from the session results that joined so many different ideas and perspectives, a question comes to authors' mind:

- Is the introduction of Sustainability in Engineering Education curricula an achievable outcome or a utopia?

To contribute to the answer to this question, the authors presents this paper findings that are, mainly, based on the papers and presentations exploration of different approaches and strategies towards EESD in similar degrees but totally different contexts (North America, South America, and Europe). Also, results of teams discussion formed during this session are presented. Among the participants of the session were some first-year students of engineering.

3. STUDY CONTEXT

This section presents the study context where this study was based that resulted, mainly, from a debate session related with Sustainability. The debate session objective and organization as also the driving questions raised in the debate are exposed.

3.1. Debate session objective and organization

Beyond the regular paper sessions, the referred conference included debate sessions to stimulate the conference participants' discussion. A total of 16 participants (among authors' papers invited, regular participants and students) attended this session. The moderator/facilitator organized three teams with five, six and four members (*Fig. 1*). At least, one author 'paper was on each team, as well, a student.

Fig. 1. Teams working (picture intentionally blurred for privacy purposes)

The debate session was organized in three main parts:

- 1) Contributors of each case study presented their findings and approaches in five minutes or less. Also, they launched one or two driving questions for the debate, according to findings from his/her paper. Main questions were registered and prioritized by consensus for the next phase.
- 2) Driving questions were registered after each presentation on the whiteboard, to facilitate the discussion phase and debate was started. A summary of consensus or disagreements reached was done for each team.
- 3) A short sum-up of main conclusions and ideas was developed altogether. It was tried to reach some answers (or new deeper questions) from the initial driving questions.

3.2. Driving questions for the discussion

In order to proceed with the debate (second part of the session), just eight driving questions, from 12 given by the authors invited were selected by consensus:

1. For an engineering education eminence level, which performance measures (in terms of efficiency, efficacy, effectiveness) could be used to evaluate sustainability competencies?
2. In addition to sustainability, should be used other drivers?
3. Sustainability approach: top down & bottom-up approaches - which should be first?
4. How to convince all instructors to include sustainability concepts in their courses?
5. How to ensure a proper scaffolding of the sustainability concepts from year to year?
6. Is there any consensus of what is a sustainable university? Is a comparison needed between universities? Or is it enough a self-comparison?
7. A great number of sustainability curriculum implementations and approaches but, how are students going to learn sustainability if the university is not sustainable?
8. Great efforts for cooperation for development in other countries, but what about solving real local problems?

Each team discussed a different group of questions, using a flip chart to collect the main ideas. Then, they were presented to all participants to be discussed.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section introduces the main key ideas from the papers and presentations as also the debate findings from each team.

4.1. EESD cases and studies key ideas

Each author had different objectives with the papers they submitted to the conference as can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Key ideas from papers and presentations

Countries	Key ideas
Brazil	Innovative experiences and proposals in EE for sustainability applied in a case of a Production Engineering program of a Brazilian university anchored on small projects (8) during the whole program.
Canada	Framework for implementing a sustainability curriculum in an Engineering Technology program. This framework should be implemented through a top-down and a bottom-up approach.
Portugal	Study of integration of sustainability in the engineering programs and courses of a Portuguese university through information contents in the university website. The authors revealed that very few programs and courses integrate sustainability.
Spain	Study of the contributions of different universities approaches to sustainability and social responsibility reports. This contribution was measured by sustainability assessment tools.

In the case of Brazil and Canada, the authors presented case studies of how they integrated or planned to integrated sustainability in specific engineering programs. Specifically, in the Brazil case, they considered that through projects, students could measure the sustainability performance by measuring the efficiency, efficacy, effectiveness and eminence level of these projects [31]. In the case of Canada, the authors also presented a framework to be used to integrate sustainability concepts into several courses of an Engineering Technology program [32]. They called this “Timeless Engineer Framework” where they defined “timeless engineer” as someone who is able to adjust to the needs of the world’s dynamic challenges in order to create solutions that are consistent with the needs of current and future generations. This framework was not implemented at the time the author presented the paper.

In the cases of Portugal and Spain, the authors presented a more general view about sustainability. The authors from Portugal present the sustainability in engineering programs in their institution [10,33] and conclude that just a small percentage considered sustainability theme in their contents, in spite of sustainability initiatives in the university such as sustainability report, sustainability research centers, among others. The authors from Spain[34] presented a study developed by a sustainable engineering research team at Spanish university based on different university approaches to sustainability and university social responsibility reports. Their main objective was to better understand how to advance and measure sustainability in a university and the important role that students may play. They highlighted the important role of PBL as learning-by-doing methodology capable of enabling students understanding the SD.

4.2. Results of teams discussion

The results of the discussion of the teams were presented to the other participants in flip charts. These results were explained by each team at the moment they presented the flip chart to the others participants.

Team 1 answered to the questions 1 and 2 (section 3.2). Their filled flip chart exposed a need to have answers based on real facts (a real problem) to convince teachers and students in a reciprocal way to distinguish sustainable from what was not sustainable. Also, they considered a need of a system approach through a formation of a task force

of consultants involving rectors, deans, teachers and students to produce a document with sustainability types and to evaluate them. Also, their opinion about how to teach were that students must teach students and sustainability evaluation must be mandatory. In order to achieve this, teachers must be trained in sustainability competencies and should be motivated to learn such competencies. In order to achieve this, teachers must be trained in sustainability competencies and should be motivated to learn such competencies (considered a driver).

Team 2 answered to questions 6, 7 and 8 (section 3.2). They showed two perspectives: 1) students are not able to be sustainable professionals if their academic environment is not. According to this team, it is necessary to instill sustainability mind-set; 2) joining forces of students' initiatives (developed in-class) and governmental support.

Team 3 discussed questions 3, 4 and 5 (section 3.2) and their opinion on these was that sustainability definition could have many meanings for different people. Nevertheless, ethical aspects, change minds and attitude should be present in all people to see sustainability in all dimensions, as referred in the literature review (section 2). Also, they considered that a bottom-up approach is better, starting with small projects and scaling up. Of course, this idea of bottom-up was not shared by all participants that considered both approaches are necessary, as also referred in the literature section.

To conclude this part, answers to the questions were marginally achieved what reinforces the difficulty to have direct responses to the questions formulated. But, at one point, they seemed to agree: all stakeholders (students, teachers, rectors, deans, society) must be involved in the on-going discussions and a mindset shift is needed because there are many universities where this did not yet happen. Involving all and with the proper mindset, sustainability integration in EE could be an achievable outcome. Right now, is still more a utopia than reality, but it was possible to see through some examples (e.g. case from Brazil) this can rather be achieved and come reality. It also seems consensual that the learning methodologies to concretize this achievement are learning-by-doing approaches or active learning. These methodologies seem a more suitable approach because involves the students in their own learning.

A lot of questions and challenges, also raised in the debate and that remained without an answer were: What should be the contents of courses/programs and how they should be related to integrating sustainability issues in a natural way? How to put the sustainability in the learning outcomes? What learning methodologies/tools to use in Higher Education Institutions in order to effectively change students' roles from spectators to sustainability key actors and change agents? The session revealed to be a short time-frame to discuss so many important topics related with sustainability.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper intended to give a contribution to the debate about introducing Sustainability in the EE curricula. The authors identified two case studies and two more general studies presented in an EE conference organized in 2016. The case studies focused on specific programs of specific universities of Brazil and Canada and the studies were developed in Portugal and Spain. The case study from Brazil is successful implemented, while Canada case was not and his author was afraid of the difficulties they will face (e.g. teachers' resistance). The other two studies showed that there is an effort to integrate sustainability in EE but more is needed. Though the different context and country, it seems concerns are the same: EESD and how it has been implemented and could be implemented. Also, how this should be achieved to form "timeless engineers" that attend sustainability issues in their professional practice. Active learning

methodologies, and, in particular, PBL seems to provide a good solution defended by many authors, including the ones involved in this study.

It was also clear that the sustainability integration in curricula implies a mindset that is not yet achieved in all, and needs to be worked out, because, as stated earlier, true learning about sustainability involves, firstly, developing in individuals the understanding and appropriation of the values of individual sustainability and the ability to change oneself intentionally. As Colombo [14] said, based on Morin [35] this change needs to start at one point, and it seems that the best is with teachers, through training in the subject, which is corroborated by many authors. However, continues without being addressed. This was also one of the questions raised by the participants in the debate: Should we teach teachers to teach sustainability? The answer is yes, because, after all, teachers are more near to the students and act more directly in teaching, research, extension, but, mainly, in the construction/reconstruction of the curricular structures. Also, teachers have a role both in the top-down and bottom-up processes of integrating sustainability. These processes, which, as shown by several authors, including those analyzed here, must be worked on two lines. It must be a movement from the base, but also must be supported and institutionalized by the dome.

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